

Mediterranean challenges for food safety and authenticity of **HONEY**

« If bees were to disappear,
humanity would only have four
years left »
Albert Einstein

Handbook

Mediterranean challenges for food safety and authenticity of honey

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Preamble

This Handbook is a one of products of the MEDIFIT project, funded by the Horizon 2020 - PRIMA joint program, which is focused on the development and application of solutions for food systems and water resources in the Mediterranean basin. The EU PRIMA MEDIFIT project focuses on the valorization of two Mediterranean products, honey and cheese. In order to improve marketing and strengthen the quality and image of these products as well as consumer confidence, MEDIFIT has the general objective of enabling the traceability and control of the authenticity of traditional Mediterranean foods using the latest technologies, analytics and software (Figure 1).

The MEDIFIT consortium, involving 6 Mediterranean countries and 12 socio-economic partners, has the mission to develop a flexible, modular and standards-based software framework that provides end users with the necessary communication interfaces and web software solutions and facilitates the use of innovative analytical methods to assess the traceability and integrity of foods and confirm the authenticity of goat's and sheep's honey and cheeses.

Figure 1. Overall concept of MEDIFIT Project.

Food fraud, including the more defined subcategory of economically motivated adulteration, is a public-health food risk that is growing in awareness, concern, and danger. Each food fraud incident has the potential to threaten consumers' well-being but also undermine confidence in the EU food market. The impact may be higher for the Mediterranean traditional food products considering that they are generally recognized for their high nutritional and sensory value. The recent example of the honey fraud between China and US of relabelled filtered honey (free of pollen) to remove traces of its origins is a characteristic example of a traceability flaw. Milk and honey are among the top 6 products that are more at risk of food fraud, while in the monthly Food Fraud summary of the EU honey and milk products (cheese) are the most frequently reported foods. For example, foreign sugars were found 1.4 times in every 10 honey samples tested by the European Joint Research Centre, according to research published in December 2016. Other common adulterations of honey with potential safety, or economic impact include: artificial coloring, unjustified organic labels and fake geographical and botanical origin. In the case of cheese, apart from the geographical origin, the use of bovine milk instead of ovine and microbial contaminations are common problems.

The overarching objective of MEDIFIT is to enable traceability, authenticity control of traditional Mediterranean foods integrating innovative analytical methods and digital technologies. To accomplish that, the consortium linked Decision Support Systems (DSSs) to a cloud-based Distributed Data and Service Integration BackBone (DDSIBB) providing access to decentralized food integrity information repositories. MEDIFIT implemented this IT-standards-driven solution for food integrity scenarios in two Mediterranean food chains: honey and cheese products by adopting a multi-actor approach from farm to fork.

Introduction

Save the bees! Beekeeping is essential for food security, poverty reduction, health, environmental protection and plant pollination. Indeed, it plays a vital role in the development of rural areas, the preservation of ecosystems, the maintenance of plant biodiversity and ecology in general, and, at the same time, contributes to increasing agricultural production yields. It has been estimated that pollination by insect pollinators including *Apis mellifera* bees contributes to the production of around a third (35%) of the world's food supply (IPBES, 2016; Murphy, et al., 2022), and consequently to a healthy, balanced diet for the world's population. Indeed, cultivated plants that depend entirely or partially on insect pollinators, including bees, are important sources of bioactive molecules, beneficial in human nutrition: they contain over 90% of vitamin C, all lycopene and almost all antioxidants such as b-cryptoxanthin and b-tocopherol, vitamin A and related carotenoids, calcium and fluorine, as well as a large proportion of folic acid (Eilers et al. 2011).

Honey is a highly appreciated natural and traditional food product. Codex Alimentarius CXS 12-1981 defines it as a "sweet substance, produced by *Apis mellifera* bees from the nectar of flowers or secretions of living plants, which the bees collect, transform by combining them with their specific substances and store in honeycombs for ripening and maturation". Consumers are increasingly aware of the impact of a healthier diet on their health, particularly with the COVID-19 crisis, and seek out nutritious food products such as honey (Jribi et al., 2021). Honey consumption is motivated not only by its sensory characteristics, but also by its high nutritional and medicinal properties. In fact, the health benefits of honey have been clearly demonstrated by improving, for example, diabetes mellitus, heart health, wound healing, antioxidant status in blood and cancer (Samarghandian et al. 2017; Gündoğdu et al., 2019; Ranneh et al., 2021). Demand for honey and hive products has therefore become significant. Furthermore, the beekeeping sector contributes to meeting the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the United Nations Agenda 2030, including SDG 2: Eradicate hunger, Ensure food security, Improve nutrition and Promote sustainable agriculture, SDG3: Enable all people to live in good health and promote well-being for all at all ages, SDG5: Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls, SDG8: Promote sustained, shared and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all, SDG12: Establish sustainable consumption and production patterns, and SDG15: Conserve and restore terrestrial ecosystems, ensuring their sustainable use, Manage forests sustainably, Combat desertification, Halt and reverse land degradation and halt biodiversity loss.

Nevertheless, beekeeping and its products are currently undermined by a number of biotic and abiotic factors. These factors affect bees and their products either in combination or on their own. Abiotic climatic factors such as extreme temperatures, relative humidity, lack of water, deforestation of melliferous plants, human factors such as poor beekeeping practices, synthetic pesticides, diseases and arthropod pests have led to the decline of bee colonies and their products. At the same time, global, regional and local market demand for honey and other products of the hive has grown

considerably in recent decades, as it is important for a wide variety of uses and applications in many sectors of the food, pharmaceutical and cosmetics industries. Honey consumption has increased in recent years, not only for its sensory attributes, but also for its nutritional and health benefits. As a result, honey is one of the most adulterated food products in the world, due to fraudulent production practices and false labeling of the product's origin. In addition to its negative economic consequences, this food fraud undermines food safety, authenticity and quality. According to APIMONDIA (2021), the official method, EA-IRMS (AOAC 998.12) does not anymore allow the detection of honey adulteration with C3-type sugars, becoming an outdated and inappropriate detection method, therefore exposing the global market to huge food fraud.

In this context, the EU PRIMA MEDIFIT has worked on innovative detection methods and IT-standards-driven solutions to improve product safety and authenticity.

The present handbook aimed at tackling Mediterranean challenges in the beekeeping sector on one hand, and on the other hand, at promoting the MEDIFIT digital solution for a better food safety and traceability, by identifying policy instruments, governance mechanisms and institutional changes required to foster transitions towards a new paradigm of digital food companies in a longer term perspective, as well as by proposing novel policy strategies.

Key figures for the world beekeeping sector

Beekeeping plays an interesting socio-economic, environmental and cultural role in our societies (Aryal, 2020; Figure 1).

Figure 1: Schematic representation of ecosystem services provided by honey bee (Aryal, 2020)

At the socio economic level, beekeeping contributes to agricultural productivity (Aryal, 2020). This contribution takes the form of self-employment for young entrepreneurs, rural and forest populations (especially women), the production of honey and other hive products (pollen, beeswax, royal jelly, propolis and venom). Moreover, bee pollination (regulating service) can enhance agricultural production by increasing the quality and quantity of crops, thereby improving farmers' incomes and food security.

Beekeeping can support the local economy by providing local products and generating income not only for beekeepers and workers involved in the beekeeping value chain, but also for farmers and herders, as a secondary or complementary activity. In fact, this activity adapts more easily to the constraints of low credit and limited access to land compared to other agricultural activities (Cristina

and Molly, 2015). For professional beekeepers, honey production is the main activity, while swarm and pollen production can be a secondary activity. Beekeepers may sell their honey directly to consumers, specialty stores, or restaurants. In addition to honey production, the other products of the hive - pollen, propolis, beeswax, etc. - are now being transformed into high potential food and cosmetic products: they can be produced and sold locally, creating a diversification of income. Finally, agrotourism is also a source of income diversification for beekeepers who share their passion for bees and honey and introduce local and foreign tourists to their trade and products. As shown in Figure 1, it is also a cultural service helping deepen knowledge of common people, students, and scientists (Aryal, 2020). In many ways, beekeeping can be seen as a reliable source of alternative income and can help communities achieve economic stability.

Beekeeping also creates jobs for self-employed or salaried beekeepers, young graduates, rural women, cooperatives or companies that produce, process and market beekeeping products. Adding value to beekeeping products can also help create new businesses and jobs in the agri-food, cosmetics and nutraceuticals sectors.

Furthermore, Beekeeping is a sustainable form of agriculture that provides rural populations with a source of income (primary or supplementary). In this respect, these populations have economic reasons to preserve biodiversity, maintain natural habitats or modify them to stimulate honey production.

1.1 Honey production

World human population has expanded by 144% from 3.1 billion in 1961 to 7.5 billion in 2017 (Phiri et al., 2022), and is expected by 2050 to reach 9.7 billion (United Nations, 2022). The agricultural sector has to ensure global food security by providing food in quantity and quality, and by preserving natural resources. In this context, to meet growing consumer demand, average annual global honey production has increased from 1.25 million tons in 2000 to 1.77 million tons in 2020 (Statista, 2022). Honey production developed in all continents, particularly in Asia and South America. According to FAO (Figure 2), the main producers are: China (27% of global production), European Union (12%), Turkey (5%) and Argentina (4%). The size of the global honey market has been estimated at US\$ 8.17 billion in 2021, with a forecast of around US\$ 12 billion by 2028 (Statista, 2022).

Figure 2: World honey production by country in 2020 (Statista, 2022)

Beekeeping is a booming sector in the world but is considered as a small sector but crucial for the agricultural sector in particular for its pollination services. The number of beekeepers worldwide in 2020 is estimated at 6.6 million, with over 50 million hives (Table 1).

The European beekeeping sector is the second largest honey producer after China, with approximately 275 000 tons of honey, approximately 19 million beehives and 615 000 beekeepers in 2020 (Figure 2). The number of hives has increased by +5.5% between 2003 and 2018 (EC, 2020). Greece accounted for 19.1% of total production, followed by Spain (16%), France (10.4%), and Italy (8.4%). Only 4 % of European beekeeping units have more than 150 hives: their average number of hives is 406 in Spain and 165 in Greece (EC, 2020).

Turkey is the second largest country producing honey, after China: its honey production was 109,330 tons in 2019 with 8,128,360 beehives and around 57,000 registered beekeepers, making Turkey one of a few self-sufficient countries in beekeeping, according to Turkish Beekeepers` Association (80% in migratory conditions according to Beekeepers` Association of Turkey).

In Tunisia, the beekeeping sector contributes 0.1% of national GDP and 1% of agricultural GDP. Average annual honey production is estimated at 2,360 tons in 2021. It increased by 57% between 2011 and 2021. According to the Tunisian Ministry of Agriculture (OEP, 2022), there are around 13,200 beekeepers in 2022, 65% of whom have fewer than 50 hives. Only 21.1% of beekeepers (>100 hives) were professionals in 2021 (Table 1), although the rate of professionalization has increased by 150% between 2016 and 2021. In terms of professional groups, they are poorly organized into cooperatives (Giguère, 2016; Debbabi, Ben Ismail & Jmal, 2023). With regard to family/amateur and semi-professional beekeeping, according to the OEP, 60% of beekeepers are pluri-active, and 10% are amateurs: they supplement their income (Debbabi, Ben Ismail & Jmal, 2023).

Table 1 : Main Key Indicators of Beekeeping Sector (EC, 2020; MARHP, 2020; Tridge Intelligences, 2022)

Criteria	Worldwide	European Union	Spain	Turkey	Tunisia
Production of Honey (T)	1.25 million	275 000	36 394	114 113	3 473
Number of beekeepers	6,6 millions	615 000	35 000	57 000	12 000
Professional beekeepers		9.3%	22.7%		30%
Number of beehives	94 millions	19 millions	3 millions	8 millions (2020)	220 000
Type of hives	Langstroth hives: 75%	Dadant Blatt: 57% Langstroth: 4%	Langstroth or Dadant	Langstroth hives: 97,3%	Type Langstroth: 99%
Main Botanical sources			Multifloral	Multifloral Pine	Eucalyptus; multiflora; Mountain
Annual average Productivity (Kg/hive)	25	17-38	10 - 19	14-17	10
Market size	8.17 billion U.S. dollars				99% domestic consumption
Export (T/year)		20 000	8,000	6,000-7,000	250 - 300
Per capita Annual Consumption		0,8-0,9 Kg/inh. (2019)	0,4 Kg /inh. (2019)	1.2 Kg/inh. (2018)	0.2 kg / inh. (2020)

Phiri et al. (2022) have evaluated long-term trends in global managed honey bee colonies and production based on a six-decade viewpoint between 1961 and 2017. The number of colonies has increased by 85% from 49,000,000 in 1961 to 91,000,000 in 2017, as well as honey yield by 45% from 11 kg/colony to 16 kg/colony during the study period (56 years) (Phiri et al., 2022).

Figure 3: Regional changes, in percentage, of beekeeping variables and human population between 1961 and 2017 (Phiri et al. 2022)

Regionally, as shown in Figure 3, this rise was observed particularly in Asia (+297%), as well as in South America, Africa and Oceania whereas North America and Europe showed a decline. The boost in yields of honey per colony between 1961 and 2017 was remarkable in Europe (+117%), followed by Asia (+74%) and Africa (61%), whereas it was modest for North America (+6%) (Phiri et al., 2022). Average annual productivity is about 22 kg/hive in European countries, ranging from 9 kg/hive in Spain and 10 kg/hive in Greece, to 25 kg/hive in Italy and 35 kg/hive in Germany (EC, 2022), whereas it is 14.68 kg/hive in Turkey, and 10 kg/hive in Tunisia (Table 1). Around 50,000 flights of bees are needed to produce one kilogram of honey. Several factors can influence productivity, such as the availability of botanical resources, bee pests and predators, bee genetics, pre- and post-harvest management, as well as the socio-demographic conditions of beekeepers and extension and education services (Schouten & Lloyd, 2019; Schouten, 2020). Worldwide, annual honey consumption varies from 0.3 to 0.4 kg/capita in Italy, France and the United Kingdom to 1 to 1.8 kg/capita in Greece, Denmark and Portugal (Chirsanova et al., 2021). In Tunisia, honey production is mainly intended for domestic consumption (99% of production in 2021), and annual honey consumption is very low, at around 0.2 kg/capita (MARHP, 2020), compared with European countries. It is limited in particular by household purchasing power.

In addition to keeping bees and producing honey, beekeepers can also provide the following services:

- Breeding and selling swarms of bees,
- Breeding and selling queens, which are then reintroduced into the apiaries,
- Production of beeswax, in particular for use in candles,
- Production of pollen and bee bread, a mixture of pollen, flower nectar or honey, and lactic acid bacteria specific to bees, used in apitherapy,
- Production of royal jelly as a food supplement, requiring specialized beekeepers as these are queen less bee farms (nurse bees produce royal jelly to feed the larvae that will become adults, but above all for the growth of the queens, which feed exclusively on it),
- Production of propolis, used mainly in pharmacopeia,
- Production of bee venom, in particular apitoxin.

According to Phiri et al. (2022), beeswax production has expanded between 1961 and 2017, by 116% from 32 000 tons to 116 000 tons (Figure 2): it was particularly strengthened in Asia (+204%), South America (+155%) and Africa (+133%). However, a decrease (-36%) was noticed in North America. Spain, Germany, France, Italy and Greece are the main beeswax producing countries in the EU. Bee wax production amounted to 1,667 tons in Spain (2016), and 3,971 tons in Turkey (2019). In Tunisia, an increase in wax production (0.5-0.65 Kg/hive/year) has been observed since 2011, probably explained by the increase in the number of hives (OEP, 2022). According to Giguère (2016), 73% of Tunisian beekeepers recover wax. Pollen has an interesting nutritional composition: it is rich in proteins, omega-3 and omega-6 fatty acids, as well as minerals (Ca, Mg, Fe, Zn, Cu), phenolic acids, flavonoids and vitamins (Eshete, 2021). Global pollen production is estimated to be around 1500 tons per year. Actually it is commercially produced in a few countries: China, Spain, Hungary, Argentina and Brazil, and it significantly contributes to the national economy. Since it is an added value product, bee pollen marketing can contribute to small and medium scale beekeepers, to increase their earning. Countries like China, Switzerland, Spain, Brazil, Argentina, and Mexico have recognized pollen as a food product and have established their own official quality standards (Eshete, 2021).

Royal jelly, known as a “superfood”, is only consumed by the queen bee. contains proteins, bioactive peptides, lipids, phenols, flavonoids and other bioactive substances (vitamins B5 and B3, minerals). It has health benefits related to its interesting biological antioxidant, antitumor, antiaging, neurotropic, and anti-inflammatory properties (Pasupuleti et al., 2017). Therefore its use in cosmetics and functional food industries has improved its value, making it a better source of income for beekeepers. Propolis is defined as “a resinous substance produced by worker bees combining plant resins and/or fragments of newly formed buds with their salivary and wax gland secretions” (ISO/DIS 24381). It is used not only as a food product (phenolic compounds, flavonoids), but also in traditional and modern medicine, thanks to its high antioxidant and antimicrobial activities and its anticancer and anti-inflammatory properties (Pasupuleti et al., 2017). Global production of commercial bee propolis, which was around 50-150 g per colony, ranges between 150 and 200 tons a year, mostly in China, Brazil and Russia (Salatino et al., 2019). It is mostly imported by European countries.

1.2 Legislation of bee products criteria and standards

Honey legislation differs from one country to another (Table 2). It defines limits for the physicochemical, organoleptic and microscopic properties of monofloral honey and requirements as the country where the honey has been harvested. However these criteria limits can differ.

Table 2: Honey Legislation

Countries	Standard
International	Codex Alimentarius Commission in 1981, revised in 1987 and 2001
European countries	Directive 2001/110/EC, amended 2014/63/EU, relating to honey
Turkey	Turkish food codex Notification No. 2012/58 on honey. Official Journal No. 28366, 27 July 2012.
Tunisia	Tunisian standard PNT 56.12 (2016)

The Codex alimentarius (FAO/WHO) standard for honey defines honey as “natural sweet substance produced by honey bees from the nectar of plants or from secretions of living parts of plants or excretions of plant sucking insects, which bees collect, transform by combining with their specific substances and stored in honeycombs for ripening and maturation”. Composition criteria for honey are specified in Table 3, according to Codex Alimentarius.

Table 3. Codex alimentarius STANDARD FOR HONEY CXS 12-1981. Adopted in 1981, Revised in 1987, 2001, Amended in 2019, 2022

Composition criteria	Blossom Honey		Honeydew Honey
	General	Exceptions	
Moisture (%)	<20		<20
Fructose + Glucose (%)	>60		>45
Sucrose (%)	<5	<i>Medicago, Eucalyptus, Citrus sp.</i> <15	<5
Non-Water Soluble (%)	<0.1	Pressed honey <0.5	<0.1
Electrical conductivity (mS/cm)	<0.8	Chestnut, <i>Arbutus, Erica, Eucalyptus, Tilia, Calluna, Manuka and Melaleuca</i>	>0.8
HMF (meq/kg)	<50	Baker's honey <80	<50
Diastase (DN)	>8	baker's honey and honey with low natural enzyme content: >3 when HMF is less than 15 mg/kg	>8
HMF (mg/kg)	<40	baker's honey, Honeys of tropical climate and blends of these honey <80	

Regarding honey adulteration, AOAC Official Method 998.12 C-4 *Plant Sugars in Honey Internal Standard Stable Carbon Isotope Ratio* is based on the detection of C3-type sugars. This method is actually considered outdated.

International quality standards are actually available for bee products. ISO 12824 (2016) describes guidelines for quality standards of royal jelly, through organoleptic and chemical test methods. ISO 12824:2016 also specifies the production (collecting, preliminary processing and packaging) and sanitary requirements for royal jelly and the requirements of transport, storage, packaging and marking for royal jelly. ISO 24364:2023 (Royal jelly production) specifies the production of royal jelly, including production conditions, production process management, storage and transportation requirements of royal jelly. For propolis, ISO/DIS 24381 specifies the requirements of quality, analytical methods, storage, transportation conditions, and packing mark, and it is actually under preparation for its final publication. An international quality standard ISO 24382 (Bee pollen — Specifications) is currently under development.

The market price and caliber of the final product are directly influenced by the country of origin of the honey. The significance of origin is highlighted in European Union (EU) legislation, which requires the declaration of honey's origin on the label, such as "blend of EU honeys" (Directive 2001/110/EC and its amendment Directive 2014/63/EU), and also establishes quality schemes. The detailed specifications for these quality schemes, namely "Protected Designation of Origin" (PDO) and "Protected Geographical Indication" (PGI), are outlined in Regulation (EU) No. 1151/2012. These schemes emphasize the strong correlation between food quality and geographic origin. Consequently, authentic honey from a specific place, country, or region, such as Mel de Barroso PDO Portuguese honey, can command a higher price and market share. The Ambrosia portal within the EU provides a comprehensive list of PDO and PGI products. As shown in Table 4, Portugal is the EU country with the highest number for honeys (9 PDO), followed by Spain (5 PDO and 1 PGI). In Tunisia, there is only 1 PDO: Kroumirie-Mogods heather honey is a honey coming from nectars collected by bees from spontaneous and natural heather plant associations in the Kroumirie-Mogods region (MARHP, 2019).

Overall, getting these certificates can prevent food fraud and indicates the implementation by SME and industries of an effective food safety system that addresses not only hazards but also vulnerabilities related to food fraud.

Table 4: Honey PDO- and PGI certified in EU countries (Glogoveţan et al., 2021).

Country	Honey name	Label
Portugal	Mel da Serra da Lousã	PDO
	Mel da Serra de Monchique	PDO
	Mel da Terra Quente	PDO
	Mel das Terras Altas do Minho	PDO
	Mel de Barroso	PDO
	Mel do Alentejo	PDO
	Mel do Parque de Montezinho	PDO
	Mel do Ribatejo Norte	PDO
Spain	Mel dos Açores	PDO
	Miel de Galicia	PGI
	Miel de Granada	PDO
	Miel de La Alcarria	PDO
	Miel de Liébana	PDO
	Miel de Tenerife	PDO
Poland	Miel Villuercas-Ibores	PDO
	Miód drahimski	PGI
	Miód kurpiowski	PGI
	Miód spadziowy z Beskidu Wyspowego	PDO
	Miód wrzosowy z Borów Dolnośląskich	PGI
France	Podkarpacki miód spadziowy	PDO
	Miel d'Alsace	PGI
	Miel de Cévennes	PGI
	Miel de Corse - Mele di Corsica	PDO
	Miel de Provence	PGI
Slovenia	Miel de sapin des Vosges	PDO
	Kočevski gozdni med	PDO
	Kraški med	PDO
Italy	Slovenski med	PGI
	Miele della Lunigiana	PDO
	Miele delle Dolomiti Bellunesi	PDO
Greece	Miele Varesino	PDO
	Meli Elatis Menalou Vanilia	PDO
Bulgaria	Pefkothymaromelo Kritis	PDO
	Manov med ot Strandzha	PDO

1.3 Production costs and profit margins

Marketing margins are defined by production costs and profit margins: both are indicators of efficiency in the honey marketing system (Table 5).

Table 5: Costs of 1 kg of Honey (EC, 2020)

	Average Prices for Multi-floral Honey		Average Production Cost per Kg of Honey Produced
	Production site	Bulk at wholesalers	
EU (2018)	6.46		3.90
Greece (2018)	9.00	4.50	5.40
Spain (2018)	6.50	3.20	2.73
Germany (2018)	6.22	5.28	6.90
Tunisia (2021)	9.09	5.45	5.14

According to the EU parliament (EC, 2020), EU beekeepers have to deal with relatively high production costs, in comparison with their main competitors. The price structure includes the costs inherent in :

- Purchase and maintenance of hives
- Transportation costs
- Swarms, queens
- Hive treatment
- Rental / Caretaking plots
- Inputs: food products, sugar, wax, medicines, etc.
- Possibly materials/equipment to protect hives against extreme temperatures,
- Extraction equipment
- Packaging equipment and materials
- Delivery: own or subcontracted
- Rental
- Management costs
- Salaried labor
- Communication costs, if any.

Losses must be taken into account when calculating costs: they have been estimated at 30% per year in France. In Tunisia, according to Debbabi, Ben Ismail & Jmal (2023), the owners estimated colony losses of around 50%, or even more, due to the extreme heat and the drought, during Summer 2023. On the other hand, in the case of organic production, additional costs are inherent in the higher price

of colonies and queens, due to the low availability of inputs (sugar, wax, medicines) and feeding products, all of which are also derived from organic farming. Moreover, the products for the treatment of maladies, in particular parasitic wasps (in particular the *Varroa destructor*) and bees, have a lower efficacy compared to standard chemical products, causing a higher mortality rate. All these factors have a considerable impact on production costs. On the other hand, given the investments involved, sales margins are higher for organic honeys (on average 60%) than conventional ones (on average 45-55%).

1.4 Honey market: imports and exports

Honey is the most widely traded product among bee products across the world. According to EC (2022), the global import and export of honey increased steadily from 2011 to 2017. Honey imports have increased globally from 497,472 tons in 2011 to 689,095 tons in 2017. Global honey exports, on the other hand, climbed from 484,876 tons in 2011 to 651,220 tons in 2017. North America, the EU and Asia are the most important honey importers worldwide, whereas Asia, Central and South America and the Caribbean are the most important honey exporters (Figure 4).

Figure 4: The World's Honey importers (4A) and exporters (4B) in 2021 (EU, 2022)

1.5 Pollinisation services

Bees pollinate many crops, including pome fruits, berries, vegetables, nuts and oilseeds. Pollination enables plants to produce fruit and vegetables of better quality, in greater quantity and more uniformly. Due to the national geographical distribution of beehives in countries such as Spain, Turkey and Tunisia, and the practice of transhumance to several locations according to successive flowerings, beekeepers provide a pollination service for plant resources and thus promote the agricultural activities present in the territories: it's a passive, non-targeted service. There is also an active, targeted pollination service. Like in the USA (Goodrich, 2019), a new market for pollination

services has recently emerged in the Occitanie region (France) in 2015. In Greece, very few farmers (2.4%) have opted to engage pollination hives for their crops by remunerating rental fees (Marnasidis et al., 2021). The creation of such markets may provide a solution to the farmers' pollination needs and also offer additional sources of income for beekeepers. This practice is well-established in the USA, particularly for almond production (Goodrich, 2019). The pricing depends on the melliferous source and the crop. However, in Europe, these markets are relatively new, resulting in a lack of information on pricing, organization, transaction costs, contracting, and other related aspects. In Tunisia, professional beekeepers rent out sites on agricultural plots to farmers, where they place their hives. This service is contractual between farmers and beekeepers: unlike in Europe, it's the beekeepers who pay the farmer (about 1.5 Euro/month/hive (Debbabi, Ben Ismail & Jmal, 2023).

Challenges of the beekeeping sector

Nowadays, beekeepers face many challenges and are faced with a number of difficulties and constraints that limit the efficiency of honey production and the profitability of their farms. The biggest challenge is the decline in honey bee populations. Although no single factor can provide a universal explanation for this apparent decline, an overarching theme emerging from the front lines of a global research effort is that more than one factor is combining to overwhelm bee health (Rong & Sadhukhan, 2021). Among them, climate change, exposure to pesticides (Chmiel et al., 2020; Siviter et al., 2021), pathogens, particularly parasitic (Schmeller et al., 2020) and habitat loss (Rong & Sadhukhan, 2021) are the main factors contributing disproportionately to the decline of honey bee populations.

2.1 Environmental Challenges

Beekeeping must now face environmental challenges not only linked to the intensification of agriculture but also those linked to climate change. Extreme weather events, such as droughts, floods and storms, can have devastating impacts on bee colonies. According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, 2022), global temperatures are expected to rise by 1.5 degrees Celsius by 2050, and by 2-4 degrees Celsius by 2100, depending on the emission scenario. The water cycle will "speed up" as the average world temperature rises due to increased evaporation. More precipitation will result from increased water vapor in the atmosphere. Global average precipitation can rise by 7% for every degree of warming, implying a future with significantly more rain and snow, as well as a larger risk of flooding in some areas. Heavy rain events are anticipated to become 1.7 times more probable and 14% more intense with a 2°C temperature increase. Changes in precipitation, on the other hand, will not be evenly distributed. More closely, the Mediterranean region is warming 20% faster than the global average (Ali et al., 2022): precipitation will likely decrease in most Mediterranean countries by 4–22%, depending on the emission scenario. Rainfall extremes will most likely increase in the northern part of the Mediterranean region. Droughts will become more prevalent in most Mediterranean countries.

In addition, the environment and bee health are also affected by loss of biodiversity, habitat destruction and soil erosion, as well as the intensification of agricultural production requiring large

quantities of pesticides. These environmental challenges were the most cited by Tunisian beekeepers surveyed by Debbabi, Ben Ismail & Jmal (2023): the reduction in honey resources (cited by 86.3% of respondents), the abusive use of phytosanitary products (82.5%), the deterioration of climatic conditions (81.3%) and diseases, particularly of parasitic origin (28.5%) (Debbabi, Ben Ismail & Jmal, 2023).

Indeed, habitat destruction, increased intensive agriculture, and pesticide use can affect populations of bees and other pollinating insects, which can lead to loss of biodiversity and negative impact on ecosystems (Rong & Sadhukhan, 2021). In addition, the environment and health of bees may be disrupted by changes in the flowering cycles of honey plants due to climate change, by advancing or delaying flowering. This can disrupt the synchronization between bees and plants, which can reduce the amount of pollen and nectar available to bees. Climate change can also lead to a loss of floral diversity, as some plant species (nectar and pollinifers) may no longer be able to survive in changing climatic conditions. This can reduce the availability of food for bees. In Tunisia, for example, the Sousse region is characterized by an average rainfall of 350 mm/year: the decrease in precipitation in 2021 (250 mm/year) has affected the growth of honey plants which are in insufficient quantities in the region (Boussema et al., 2023). Consequently, the degradation, alteration, and even destruction of habitats have been major causes of the scarcity of species in their natural environment. The unavailability of honey plants due to the reduction of forest areas due to fires and deforestation constitutes one of the problems that beekeeping must face (Abdelkader, 2020).

Growing urbanization also plays a role in the destruction of habitats, leading in particular to a disorganization of the land structure and consumption of agricultural land . According to the UN (2020), the percentage of people living in cities is expected to reach 60% by 2030. By that time, projections predicted that a third of everyone on Earth would reside in cities that have at least 500,000 people, is anticipated to increase from 26% in urban areas in 2000 to 38% in 2030. Agricultural practices also contribute to the reduction in quantity and diversity of food sources (nectar and pollen) available to bees: these practices are essentially monocultures, early mowing of meadows, the oversimplification of crop rotations and the lack of leguminous surfaces. Thus alterations to the natural habitats of bees modify the living and reproductive conditions of wild bees. This contributes to reducing the population of wild bees, which are also important pollinators.

Insecticides and pesticides are an integral part of the agricultural system. These are the most controversial sources responsible for the decline of bees. Pesticides have a high economic benefit in agricultural systems, but they jeopardize the health of bees (Siviter et al., 2021). By foraging on crops sprayed with pesticides for phytosanitary purposes, bees can accumulate pesticides. These products can induce excess bee mortality (Siviter et al., 2021). Exposure to sub-lethal doses of a pesticide during foraging can negatively impact the health of bees and other pollinators, and disrupt their behavior. Pesticide bioaccumulation in honey bees affects detoxification genes responsible for managing environmental stress (Chmiel et al., 2020). Chmiel et al. (2020) reported that sub-lethal

exposure to pesticides such as neonicotinoids and thiamethoxam can negatively affect reproduction, immunity, physiology and cognition. From the reproductive cycle, this sublethal exposure to pesticides can also alter the reproductive potential of queens, and hinder larval development. In Tunisia, surveys with beekeepers and the OEP of MEDIFIT team, Debbabi, Ben Ismail & Jmal (2023) have highlighted the deleterious effects on the health of bees, the anarchic use of phytosanitary products, and the abusive use of insecticides in the fields. Indeed, some products used in Tunisia available in the informal market are strictly prohibited in Europe.

2.2 Sanitary Challenges

Honeybees are often exposed to diseases and parasites that can be transmitted between bee colonies, leading to economic losses (Schmeller et al., 2020). These are bacterial diseases (American foulbrood, *Paenibacillus larvae*, and European foulbrood, *Melissococcus*), fungal (*Nosema apis* and *Nosema ceranae*), viral (deformed wing virus, chronic paralysis virus, acute paralysis virus, black cell), protozoa, insect pests, parasitic mites (*Varroa destructor*, *Nosema apis* and *N. ceranae*) and vertebrate pests. Most of these infectious agents have been detected in Tunisia (Pirk et al., 2016; Abdelkader, 2020). Among all other pests, the *Varroa* mite represents a significant threat to commercial beekeeping throughout the world, observed worldwide (Boncristiani et al., 2020; Chauhan et al., 2021) including the Mediterranean region: Egypt (Kugonza, 2020), Turkey (Kösoğlu et al. 2019), Spain, and Greece. In Spain, in autumn 2016, *Varroa* was detected in 86% of the apiaries and 53.5% of the colonies investigated. Only 50.0% of the apiaries presented very mild or no levels of infestation ($\leq 1\%$) and 20.0% of them presented moderate to very severe parasitism, a lower percentage than that recorded in the previous season (28.1%) (EC, 2021). It is an infestation to be declared to the OIE (Pirk et al., 2016). It spreads very quickly and causes serious damage to its host colonies, where it reproduces inside capped brood cells to protect it from most acaricides (Chauhan et al., 2021). It is responsible for the loss of more than 50% of *Apis mellifera* bee colonies worldwide (Chauhan et al., 2021). Bacterial diseases (European and American foul borne FB) can cause severe larval losses and colony collapse and should also be reported to the OIE. AFB and EFB are present in numerous countries on all continents where honey bee breeding is developed (Boncristiani et al., 2020). They include all the countries of the Mediterranean region, excepting Egypt: EFB has not been detected so far. American bee larval blight (AFB; American bee wilt, severe bee wilt, bee plague) is the most widespread and extremely dangerous larval disease of honeybees, resulting in high morbidity (Matović et al., 2023). These pathogens have been identified in countries on all continents (Boncristiani et al., 2020) and are therefore of economic importance to global beekeeping (Matović et al., 2023).

Implementing appropriate pathogen management and preventive control strategies in hives, particularly against the destructive *V. destructor* mite, is critical to maintaining the health and

productivity of bee colonies. Bee health and disease prevention strategies are based on Good Agricultural Practice (GFP) and Good Veterinary Practice (GVP) in bee production (Hendriks et al., 2009). Nekoei et al. (2023) examined management and treatment options to reduce pathogen burden or infection levels. Synthetic acaricides are actually used to fumigate Varroa mites, but residues and resistance have been observed in all hive products in recent years (Nekoei et al., 2023). Therefore, sustainable organic biocontrol agents against Varroa mites are widely used. They are based on instillation, fumigation or spraying of organic acids (oxalic and formic acid) and thymol essential oils from medicinal plants, but their effects depend on climatic and hive conditions as well as the application method leading to partial or temporary effects (Giese and Giese, 2013; Nekoei et al., 2023). Thymol (Apiguard, Thyme essential oil) has acaricidal activity and repellent effects (Gracia et al., 2017). Loucif-Ayad et al. (2010) in Algeria and Leza et al. (2015) in Spain have shown better effectiveness of treatments based on Apiguard® when compared with Apivar® (500 mg of amitraz/strip, Veto Pharma). However, Apiguard® appeared to be less effective in warm climates (Leza et al., 2015). Recently, a honey bee recombinant DNA vaccine was developed for oral treatment of V-destructor (Giese & Giese, 2013). Furthermore, the European Food and Safety Authority (EFSA) recommendations on hygiene are based not only on the handling of bee colonies but also on the disinfection of equipment (Hendriks et al., 2009). The European Food Safety Authority also recommends the destruction of affected or suspected colonies and contaminated material to ensure the rapid elimination of infectious disease outbreaks (Hendriks et al., 2009).

Most management and treatment strategies to be implemented depend on beekeeper initiative and local government regulations, which can vary significantly from country to country. Beekeepers' actions and actions in apiaries depend on their perception of threats (Jacques et al., 2017). In fact, Jacques et al. (2017) found a strong link between colony loss and education and training of European beekeepers. Professional beekeepers are able to quickly identify symptoms, especially those caused by V. destructor and FB, and implement appropriate control measures to ensure the survival of the colony.

Furthermore, professional beekeepers feel more concerned about diseases affecting their livestock as well as problems with predators and parasites than amateur beekeepers. This is probably due to different profitability objectives between amateurs and professionals. Mortality caused by diseases and parasites is very detrimental for professional beekeepers, who must make a living from their farm. In addition, as professionals have less time to devote to each hive, they are more attentive to the health aspect.

There are also risks affecting consumer nutrition and health. More than 70% of plant crops rely on pollination, and a decline in pollination will affect the quantity and quality of human nutrition. Furthermore, honey may contain various contaminants from the environment or beekeeping practices (Al-Waili et al., 2012; Savarino et al., 2020). If these contaminants are ingested by consumers, they may cause health problems to consumers. These pollutants include pesticide

residues, heavy metals (lead, cadmium, and mercury), organic pollutants, polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) and antibiotic residues, and pathogenic microorganisms.

The presence of pesticides in food has become a major public health problem. In their review, Murcia-Morales et al. (2022) evaluated 50 representative monitoring studies, carried out in different regions of the world over the period 2011-2021, which made it possible to detect 363 pesticide and biocide residues in honey and other beehive products. The most common are insecticides such as chlorpyrifos, imidacloprid, dimethoate and tebuconazole. Sources of honey contamination are the environment and beekeeping practices. Al-Waili et al. (2012) found that contamination of honey and other bee products with varroacids is greater than that from the environment. In terms of human health, pesticide residues cause genetic mutations and cellular damage, negatively impacting the health of consumers. In addition to public health problems, their presence in beekeeping products alters quality.

The presence of microorganisms in honey can influence not only its quality but also consumer safety. These microorganisms come from bees, nectar or external sources. Pollen, bee gut, humans, equipment, containers, wind and dust are possible sources of microbial contamination. Due to the physicochemical characteristics of honey, only bacterial spores such as those of *Clostridium botulinum*, responsible for infant botulism, and *Bacillus* sp., have been detected in honey samples, in several studies as reported by Al-Waili et al. (2012), Silva et al. (2017) and Ebrahimi et al. (2022). *Clostridium botulinum* is particularly harmful to children under one year old because their immune systems are not yet developed. *Penicilliums* and *Aspergillus flavus* have been reported as the most detected molds in honey samples (Silva et al., 2017). These molds can be pathogenic and pose health problems to susceptible people (Ebrahimi et al., 2022).

Antibiotic residues in honey have become a major concern for consumers. Several studies have highlighted the presence of antibiotics in honey (Alla, 2020; Draiaia, et al., 2015; Reybroeck, 2018; Savarino et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2022). The Chinese study by Wang et al. (2022) showed high detection frequencies and/or concentrations of quinolones, sulfonamides or the sum of all antibiotics in honey samples produced in China and the least expensive ones. These molecules are likely to cause direct toxic reactions in consumers, while others can cause allergic or hypersensitivity reactions (Lima et al., 2020). In addition, they can promote the spread of resistant microbial strains. Inappropriate beekeeping practices are responsible for the presence of these antibiotic residues in honey and bee products. Indeed, the threat of bacterial diseases by American foulbrood and European foulbrood, and the growing demand for honey have probably led many beekeepers to randomly use cocktails of antibiotics at often very inappropriate doses and at varying periods, leading in some cases to significant contamination of honey (Lima et al., 2020).

2.3 Quality and Authenticity Challenges

One of the biggest challenges of the beekeeping sector is related to fraudulent practices. Indeed, honey is one of the most adulterated products in the world. The PRIMA MEDIFIT project (2020-2023) is particularly interested in this issue. Consumers, the honey industry, and food regulatory organizations are all interested in developing ways for determining and ensuring the authenticity of honey.

In Europe, according to the European Anti-Fraud Office, the main fraudulent practices consist of adding sugar syrups (rice, wheat or beetroot) in order to lower the price, additives and colorings or falsifying product information. traceability. According to the MEDIFIT INAT investigation, frauds can be classified into two main categories: (1) those affecting the quality of the product, and (2) those relating to the description of the marketed product, in this case, the labeling, as illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5. The different types of adulteration and fraud in honey and their positioning in the supply chain (Debbabi, Ben Ismail & Jmal, 2023)

Both honey production and origin have an impact on honey quality. The first case relates to the harvesting of honey before maturity which constitutes a non-compliant practice of harvesting and processing of honey. Honey production process's handling entails numerous procedures like centrifugation, filtering, or pasteurization. Honey filtration should be disclosed on the label, according to European Commission (EC) Directive 2001/110/EC, but this wasn't always the case.

However, a more prevalent issue is the adulteration of honey with other substances during manufacture. Due to the high market price of honey, which is a costly product, this adulteration is motivated by financial gain. In this approach, low-cost sweeteners like high-fructose corn syrup (HFCS), glucose syrup, or invert sugar syrups are mixed with honey to cut down on the amount of actual honey per packing. Another less popular fraudulent practice that reduces the nutritional content and shelf life is the addition of water.

In Tunisia, at the production level, these are mainly the problems of fraud linked to excessive feeding, according to Debbabi, Ben Ismail & Jmal (2023). In recent years in Tunisia, drought and low honey potential have led to nectar and pollen deficiencies for bees, but honey production is assured. This contradiction is an indicator of continuous feeding (365 days/365 days) by beekeepers.

The botanical origin can also have an impact on market price. In the EU, for example, there is a tendency toward honeydew honey consumption, which has resulted in a higher market price. In Tunisia, in order to deceive about the botanical origin of honey, some malicious beekeepers may use flavored sugar syrup, through a prior decoction of eucalyptus leaves for example.

Actually beekeepers are affected by a drop in production and concomitantly, by an increase in imports of low-cost honey (China, India, Egypt, etc.) in order to satisfy growing demand. Wholesalers prefer to import honey because of the relatively high price of European and Tunisian honey, and the volumes of locally produced honey. These low-cost imports are perceived by producers as unfair competition, because they put honest beekeepers at a disadvantage. The European Anti-Fraud Office (OLAF, 2023) indicated that of the 320 samples of imported honey, around 46% are strongly suspected of not being in compliance with European regulations, in particular those originating from China and Turkey. In addition, 57% of the 123 honey exporters to Europe are suspected of having adulterated their honey, and two-thirds of the 95 European importers inspected are affected by at least one suspicious batch (OLAF, 2023). This problem of fraudulent imported honey also affects Tunisia: a comparative study carried out by the Tunisian Institute of Consumption (INC, 2022) showed that all the imported honey samples analyzed are not in compliance with Tunisian regulations, particularly in the form of fake honey. Some samples revealed the presence of added sugar. Other analyzes carried out by the Ministry of Commerce on samples of imported honey from importers' warehouses have shown that some do not comply with the composition criteria and/or honey production processes. According to the Debbabi, Ben Ismail & Jmal (2023), fraudulent production practices are cited by 62.5% of surveyed Tunisian beekeepers as a constraint hindering the development of the sector. In Tunisia, an investigation carried out in 2018 by the Ben Arous regional trade directorate highlighted that nearly 80% of the honey controlled and marketed in this area is fraudulent, mostly imported. Glogoveţan et al. (2021) have stated that the geographical origin of honey (PDO and PGI) is not the most significant factor in determining its authenticity. In fact, due to their distinct and exquisite flavor, monofloral, PDO, and PGI honeys are widely regarded as

premium products and, as a result, are more vulnerable to adulteration through mislabeling and fraudulent mixing with cheaper, inferior honeys (Soares, et al., 2017).

Labeling fraud is particularly widespread throughout the world. Labels are a mandatory element of food product packaging, aimed at providing information on food quality and traceability to consumers. An investigation carried out in France by the DG CCRF also highlighted that labeling defects and other anomalies are more frequent on honeys sold directly by beekeepers or through short circuits (fairground markets, associations, catering, etc.), compared to other distribution channels (GMS). These labeling defects were linked to the absence of mention of the country of origin, to a mention of "French origin" on imported honeys, to the presence of abusive mentions (for example, "100% natural / all flowers") and incorrect names (for example, "Liquid honey" for crystallized honey) (DG CCRF, 2017). In the United States, the most common labeling defects are: the use of an incorrect "net weight" declaration; the inappropriate assertion of a "pure" floral source; and incorrect identification of honey mixed with a single floral source (Vu et al., 2022). In Serbia, 89.32% of labels were missing at least one of the mandatory information from the list provided for by the regulations (Knezevic et al. 2019). In Tunisia, surveys of beekeepers (n=80) and honey traders (n=120) highlighted not only an absence of labeling, but also a lack of various information, depending on the marketing channel concerned (Debbabi, Ben Ismail & Jmal, 2023). In fact, only 43.8% of the beekeepers surveyed said they sold their honey pre-packaged with a label. Among them, only 17.6% comply with current legislation. The information available mainly concerns the botanical origin (76.5%), the brand (55.9%) and the contact details of the producer (52.9%), as well as the composition (50%). Direct sales allow beekeepers to establish direct contact with customers and thus build a relationship of trust since 96.2% of beekeepers surveyed say they have loyal customers. This lack of application of regulations could probably be linked to the fact that the majority of honey production is sold on the local market (97.5% and 2.5% for self-consumption), through direct sales and short circuits (94.9% of the panel). Regarding labeling at points of sale and distribution, 81.7% of the traders surveyed say they affix a label to the beekeeping products sold. Among them, 72.7% say they use supplier labels and 14.5% affix their own label. 8.3% are in compliance with regulations. The information affixed is essentially the botanical origin (77.2%), the net weight (91.8%) and the name of the brand (87.3%) as well as the seller's contact details (69.1%). The quality of information was linked to the point of sale. Concerning mandatory date labeling, expiration and production dates were only affixed respectively by 14.7% and 17.6% of beekeepers, and 80.9% and 70% for traders. Optional nutritional information was provided by 32.4% of beekeepers surveyed and 11.8% of traders.

Overall, it is critical and urgent to spot honey fraud and to monitor and manage the honey quality, safety and authenticity.

Traceability as a tool to ensure honey quality and authenticity

ISO 22000:2018 standard defines food traceability as the "ability to follow the history, application, movement, and location of an object through specified stage(s) of production, processing, and distribution". According to the Codex Alimentarius Commission (CAC, 2006), food traceability is defined as the "ability to track the progress of a product through the food chain, including production, processing, and distribution". In the EU, the General Food Law No 178/2002 (EU, 2002) adopts a one-step-back-one-step-forward approach. Tunisian regulation defines food traceability as the "ability to trace, through all stages from primary production to distribution, the path of a food, animal feed, or substance intended to be incorporated or likely to be incorporated into a food or animal feed" (Law No. 25 of February 26, 2019 relating to the health safety of foodstuffs and animal feed, JORT of March 22, 2019). Similarly the definition of traceability, as per the American Production and Inventory Control Society (APICS), encompasses a broader scope that ensures food safety. Qian et al. (2020) have analyzed terminology and functionality features across these various definitions. These systems operate through forward and backward traceability or a track and trace approach. Common characteristics and terms are repeated in various definitions, such as the 'trace' or 'flow' and the 'movement' or 'path' of an 'entity', 'steps', 'object', 'batch', 'food', 'feed', 'substance', or 'item'. When these definitions are combined, traceability related to food products can be defined as the "ability to access any or all information related to the product throughout its entire life cycle by means of recorded identifications" (Qian et al., 2020).

Food fraud mitigation strategies are based either on detection, combat or prevention. Safety management systems such VACCP and HACCP can support these strategies and include food traceability in their tools. Moreover, promoting and recognizing PDO and PGI honeybee products is primarily concerned with the traceability and authenticity of the products (Soares et al., 2017; Glogoveţan et al., 2021).

3.1 Analytical tools for honey quality and authenticity

According to APIMONDIA (2022), the official method, EA-IRMS (AOAC 998.12) does not anymore allow the detection of honey adulteration with C3-type sugars, becoming an outdated and

inappropriate detection method, therefore exposing the global market to huge food fraud. Research is currently focusing on the combining trustworthy analytical methodologies and advanced chemometric technologies. Detection of adulterants such syrups relies on using chemometric-integrated spectroscopic techniques. Se et al. (2019) have reviewed these analytical techniques including nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy, infrared and Raman spectroscopy, sensor-based methods and chromatography.

In Turkey, a study by Cengiz and Durak (2019) was conducted to detect sucrose syrup adulteration in honeys, based on the use of FT-IR and PLSR. The spectroscopic method predicted a range of sucrose concentrations in honey samples ranging from 4.52 to 15.16%, and the results were validated by chromatography. Several studies have demonstrated successful applications of NIR or VIS/NIR spectroscopy for honey adulteration evaluation. Bázár et al. (2016) used GNIR spectra (1300-1800 nm) collected with a fiber optic immersion probe, to detect high-fructose corn syrup in four artisanal Robinia honeys. The PLSR models created utilizing the spectral region encompassing absorption bands related to both water and carbohydrates enabled for accurate identification of the adulterant concentration (RMSECV = 1.48; R2CV = 0.987). Huang et al. (2020) have analyzed 20 popular honey varieties from 10 Chinese provinces, by NIR and MIR spectroscopy, in conjunction with SVM and data fusion, to detect adulteration. They tested both pure honey and contaminated samples containing varying quantities of syrup, and demonstrated a better performance of intermediate-level data fusion with 100% accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity, for enhancing the detection model, than the low-level data fusion. From the MEDIFIT project, regarding honey analysis, within the work package 2 (WP2), AUTH group employed non-targeted innovative spectroscopic analytical methods combined with chemometric modeling in order to develop innovative analytical solutions to authenticate Mediterranean honeys. Specifically, the AUTH group focused on UV-Vis, FT-ATR-MIR and FT- NIR spectroscopy and Confocal Raman Microscopy (CRM). Spectra preprocessing was done with appropriate algorithms (baseline correction, smoothing, etc.) and advanced chemometrics methods such as one-class classification methods (DD-SIMCA) were used to differentiate and classify the different samples. In fact, Dimakopoulou-Papazoglou et al. (2023) have used UV-Vis spectroscopy in conjunction with multivariate statistical analysis to identify cases of honey adulteration with sugar syrups and colorants. 151 commercial samples (thyme, pine, and polyfloral honeys) were gathered from various Mediterranean nations (Greece, Malta, Spain, Tunisia, and Turkey); the remaining 58 samples of Greek thyme honey were tampered with by adding syrups and colorants. The spectral range of 220–550 nm was used to identify honey adulteration using Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Random Forest (RF), Partial Least Squares – Discriminant Analysis (PLS-DA), and Data Driven-Soft Independent Modelling of Class Analogies (DD-SIMCA). In contrast, the majority of analyzed cases yielded improved accuracy and sensitivity outcomes using DD-SIMCA models. MEDIFIT findings demonstrate the good predictive capacity of UV-Vis spectroscopy in conjunction with chemometrics for the identification of adulterated honey; hence, it may be applied as a quick, low-cost, and straightforward technique.

Fluorescence excitation-emission spectroscopy coupled with statistical tools was successfully utilized as the nondestructive and fast detection tool of adulterated honey (Dramićanin et al., 2018). Samples were collected in Serbia during winter feeding of bee colonies with a sucrose solution. Using the proposed LDA model, natural honey samples (acacias, lindens, sunflowers, and meadow mixes) were perfectly distinguished from adulterated honey samples. In five spectrum areas corresponding to aromatic amino acids, phenolic chemicals, furosine, and Maillard reaction products, pure and adulterated honey samples differed significantly.

3.2 Traceability tools

Traceability in beekeeping aims to follow the journey of honey from the hive to the final consumer, guaranteeing the quality, origin and conformity of beekeeping products. Here are listed some of the traceability systems used in beekeeping:

- **Labeling and marking:** Each jar or package of honey must be labeled with information such as the origin of the honey, the name of the producer, the date of harvest, etc. This allows consumers to know the history of the product.
- **QR Codes and Barcodes:** The use of QR codes or barcodes on packaging allows consumers to scan the product with their smartphone to obtain detailed information on the origin, beekeeping practices, certifications, etc.
- **Geographic Information Systems (GIS):** Some beekeepers use geographic information systems to map the location of their hives. This can be integrated into the traceability process to show where the honey was harvested.
- **Blockchain:** Blockchain technology can be applied to create an immutable record of all stages of the honey production and distribution process. Each transaction is recorded transparently, thus strengthening traceability.
- **Mobile Applications:** Mobile applications can be developed to allow beekeepers to enter information about harvest, hive locations, weather conditions, etc. This data can then be consulted by consumers.
- **Quality certifications:** Certifications, such as organic labels, can serve as traceability mechanisms. Certified producers must follow specific standards, and consumers can look for these certifications on packaging.
- **Hive Monitoring Systems:** Some beekeepers use sensors and tracking devices installed in hives to monitor parameters such as temperature, humidity and bee activity. This data can be integrated into traceability systems.
- **Hive Records:** Keeping detailed records on each hive, including its location, medical treatments, and harvests, also helps with traceability.

These traceability systems aim to ensure the quality, transparency and safety of beekeeping products while allowing consumers to make informed choices about the products they purchase. Adoption of these technologies may vary depending on the size of the beekeeping operation, available resources, and specific traceability requirements. Digital traceability tools cover a range of technologies and software solutions that enable a product's journey through the supply chain to be digitally tracked and documented. According to Srivastava & Dashora (2022), blockchain technology for the traceability of honey should be used from production, processing, packaging, transport till consumption. In fact, blockchain increases food supply chain transparency and consumer trust, but also comes with significant energy and financial costs. Companies must invest significant money and time in training all relevant personnel and purchasing the necessary equipment. Therefore, cost-benefit analysis is crucial (Srivastava & Dashora, 2022). Regarding digital traceability of honey and bee products, Danieli & Lazzari (2022) have reviewed IoT and blockchain tools: blockchain can be used for open traceability systems, including honey yield prediction and verification models, smart distribution systems based on blockchain technology, pollen signature verification using machine learning algorithms, and information portals accessible to end customers, all designed for sustainability and built and used worldwide.

Electronic Product Code Information Service (EPCIS) standards are quickly becoming the norm for traceability best practices (ISO/IEC 19987), enabling a better supply chain visibility. Because it ensures the scalability of the entire system while guaranteeing the tamper-proof nature of sensitive information, the food safety traceability system created by combining blockchain and EPCIS may better tackle the current food safety and authenticity problem (Lin et al., 2019). The objective is to completely document the journey of honey from the hive to the consumer, thus guaranteeing the quality and transparency of the beekeeping product.

Electronic Product Code Information Service (EPCIS) standard is rapidly becoming the standard for traceability best practices (ISO/IEC 19987), enabling a more visible supply chain. Recently, sensor reports can be included in EPCIS. Food safety traceability system created by combining blockchain and EPCIS may better tackle the current food safety and authenticity problem. This combined approach may allow for the scalability of the entire system while supporting the tamper-proof nature of sensitive information (Lin et al., 2019).

MicroHibro is a web-based tool dedicated to enhancing food quality and safety. Developed by the PAID AGR-0170 (HIBRO) team at the University of Córdoba (Spain), it has received support from several regional, national, and international projects. The software is available at www.microhibro.com and free access after registration.

This tool aims at supporting food safety and quality in food industries, research, and official food control. Apart from food safety applications, MicroHibro is used as an educational resource,

facilitating the training in fundamental concepts in both predictive microbiology and Quantitative Microbial Risk Assessment (QMRA) domains (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Main page of Microhibro tool

Currently, MicroHibro comprises four modules that cover predictive microbiology models, shelf-life models, farm-to-fork models and sampling plans (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Four main modules of Microhibro

The prediction module includes predictive models describing microbial growth, inactivation, or transfer of foodborne pathogens and spoilage microorganisms. Models are stored in a dedicated database based on the MicroHibro and FSKX standard (Filter et al., 2022; González et al., 2019; Plaza-Rodríguez et al., 2018). Models can be selected through a navigation tree, a search window applying different filters such as model category, food, and parameters, or a decision system based on answers to specific questions. From the selected model, MicroHibro returns predicted kinetic parameters, such as the maximum growth or inactivation rate, latency time, maximum population density, and D-value, among others depending on the type of model. Predictions are also represented graphically, reflecting those changes in the model parameters (Figure 8). Models can be also challenged with data provided by the user, so as to validate MicroHibro models for specific user applications, related to particular food products or food processing conditions.

The shelf-life is a specific feature which allows users to validate product shelf-life based on sensory, physicochemical, and microbiological criteria. These attributes can be predicted with specific models included in the MicroHibro database. Attributes can be predicted jointly providing users with a comprehensive analysis of the effect of distinct shelf-life factors.

Figure 8 : Microhibro's predictive module dashboard

The farm-to-table module is specifically dedicated to develop food chain models able to represent the effect, in combination, of different food processes or food stages. The module can be used to predict the dynamics of sensory, physicochemical and microbiological parameters (Figure 9). The construction of farm-to-table models is carried out with models contained in MicroHibro data base. Each food step is described by selecting a specific model and joining it to the previous one using a object-based system.

Figure 9 : From farm-to-table module dashboard in Microhibro

The sampling plans module provides users with a range of tools to create, assess, and enhance sampling plans, as well as formulate microbiological criteria for food. Practical example are available to facilitate the development of sampling plans and microbiological criteria by introducing risk metrics such as Performance Objectives (PO) and Food Safety Objectives (FSO). Additionally, the application aids users to design customized sampling plans through a guided system.

In MEDIFIT, MicroHibro has adopted the EPCIS standard, based on FSKX scheme, enabling it to share models and predictions in an EPCIS repository. With this development, MicroHibro capabilities can be integrated in digital traceability systems, providing food stakeholders and food players with predictive tools to assess microbial food safety and prevent foodborne cases in real time and in a transparent manner.

In addition, mobile apps facilitate the reporting of food safety concerns by enabling users to access secure information concerning food recalls and outbreaks of foodborne illness. Therefore, using digital tools can assist to increase the efficiency and efficacy of efforts related to food safety, which will eventually serve to safeguard customers and guarantee the security of the food supply.

3.3 The MEDIFIT digital solution

Food traceability and integrity in Mediterranean supply chains are supported by the Digital Platform for Food Integrity and Traceability of Relevant Mediterranean Supply Chains, or MEDIFIT, which makes use of cutting-edge analytical tools and methodologies. Its purpose is to give food safety experts up-to-date information and analysis so they can track food goods as they move through the supply chain, from farm to fork, and spot any problems with quality or safety. Development and implementation of innovative solutions, technological tools, digital solutions, and protocols are crucial for food safety on a global scale. Focusing on products with high added-value and nutritional value is significant for biodiversity conservation. In this context, the MEDIFIT project developed an interlinked digital platform for food integrity and traceability of relevant Mediterranean supply chains. MEDIFIT project is a pioneering tool on improving traceability, authenticity control of Mediterranean honey integrating innovative analytical methods and digital technologies.

Utilizing a blend of cutting-edge analytical methods, including blockchain technology, data mining, and machine learning, it examines food samples to determine their provenance and path through the supply chain. The MEDIFIT solution is based on novel not-target methods (NIR, Raman, RMN, etc.) in combination with the application of cutting-edge digital technology. Utilizing a blend of cutting-edge analytical methods, including blockchain technology, data mining, and machine learning, it examines food samples to determine their provenance and path through the supply chain. The Risk Assessment Modelling and Knowledge Integration Platform (RAKIP) Initiative aims at supporting researchers working on food safety and integrity. RAKIP Initiative has exemplified a strategy for future information exchange and integration for the microbial risk assessment domain. In MEDIFIT, EPCIS was synergistically integrated along with FSKX (Food Safety Knowledge Exchange) by RAKIP and MicroHibro prediction tool. Advanced data analysis techniques, such as machine learning and artificial intelligence, have the potential to completely transform data analysis and modeling in the field of food technology, much as they have in environmental science and engineering. MEDIFIT solution provides a transparency platform for authenticity of cheese and honey. Including Blockchain

characteristics to any value chain ensures traceability so that adulteration is prevented. EPCIS (Electronic Product Code Information Services) 2.0, as a standard, represents a leap towards enhancing visibility across the supply chain, especially in sectors like food.

The benefit of MEDIFIT is its capacity to deliver accurate and timely traceability data, which can enhance the efficacy and efficiency of food safety initiatives. Additionally, it can assist in identifying any hazards to food safety and quality problems early in the supply chain, enabling the taking of corrective action in a timelier manner.

Therefore MEDIFIT solution will help to answer and address these challenges for honey and cheese sectors, and support new value chains by:

- **Addressing Authenticity & Counterfeiting**

It offers an authentic record of each product's journey. For sectors like honey and cheese where authenticity is paramount, this system ensures that every item can be traced back to its origin, combating counterfeits and adulterated products.

- **Sustainable Production & Sourcing**

MEDIFIT Solution captures data from the point of origin to ensure transparency. This transparency allows producers and consumers to verify sustainable and ethical sourcing of ingredients and materials. E.g., by ensuring that a certain cheese is produced from free-grazing animals or honey is harvested using eco-friendly methods. With the farm-to-table module of MicroHibro, the software can contribute to optimize food processes through a microbiological perspective.

- **Quality Assurance**

MEDIFIT Solutions utilize cutting-edge analytical methods and EPCIS, as electronic standard, improving food safety and quality assessment of Mediterranean food products. MicroHibro, a prediction tool for microbial quality and safety, has been adapted, based on EPCIS and FSKX, to be integrated in traceability systems, providing predictions and data that can be traceability, accessible and usable along the food supply chain, by food consultants, food producers and food authorities. Introducing scientific tools for food integrity assessment into the traceability systems will improve transparency and reliability in the food chain. With the inclusion of sensorReports in EPCIS 2.0, stakeholders can monitor critical parameters like temperature or humidity in real-time. For temperature-sensitive products like certain cheeses or raw honey, this ensures quality and safety standards are met throughout the supply chain.

- **Streamlined Supply Chain**

MEDIFIT Solution offers real-time visibility into the movement and status of goods. This can lead to better inventory management, reduced wastage, and timely responses to supply chain disruptions.

The sampling plans module of Microhibro can assist in creating and enhancing sampling plans, improving the efficiency of quality control processes in the supply chain. This contributes to a more streamlined and effective supply chain for cheese products.

- **Consumer Trust & Engagement**

MEDIFIT Solution enhances consumer trust through transparent data. The educational component of Microhibro can be used to outreach several food-related players, from farm to fork, providing proof of application of the efficiency of using innovative integrated food safety solutions. User-friendly tools, such as MicroHibro, can be leveraged to convey scientific results in an understandable and appealing manner, shared with different consumers and general populations, providing use cases within the food chains targeted by MEDIFIT, cheese product and honey.

By leveraging the transparent data offered by an EPCIS 2.0 repository, businesses can boost consumer trust. Additionally, they can create interactive platforms where consumers can verify product authenticity and learn about the product's journey, fostering brand loyalty.

- **New Business Models & Opportunities**

MEDIFIT Solution allows:

Data Monetization: Producers can offer access to their traceability data to third parties, such as researchers or marketers, opening new revenue streams. Microhibro's farm-to-table module can be used to assess different processes in the cheese supply chain. Producers can leverage this information to create new business models, such as premium product lines supported by Microhibro's prediction and models.

Collaborative Ventures: With a standardized system in place, businesses can easily collaborate, forming new partnerships or joint ventures. For example, a cheese producer might collaborate with a logistics company specializing in cold storage transport.

Premium Product Lines: Producers can launch premium product lines leveraging the transparency and assurance provided by MEDIFIT EPCIS 2.0, attracting a niche market willing to pay more for verified quality and authenticity.

Regulatory Compliance & Market Access

Robust traceability ensures that producers meet regulatory requirements, paving the way for easier access to international markets which have stringent traceability and quality norms.

- **Informed Decision Making**

MEDIFIT Solution provides comprehensive data for informed decision-making. Indeed, the comprehensive data collected can be analyzed to derive actionable insights. Producers can optimize their processes, reduce costs, and make informed decisions on production volumes, distribution channels, and marketing strategies. The different modules of Microhibro, including the prediction module and shelf-life module, can provide detailed information for decision-making in cheese production. Producers can optimize processes based on Microhibro's predictions and assessments.

In conclusion, the MEDIFIT solution is a cutting-edge digital platform that might completely transform the management of food traceability and integrity in Mediterranean supply chains, hence enhancing the delivery of safe and high-quality food.

Novel policy strategies, Policy instruments, governance mechanisms and institutional changes

The Mediterranean is a very suitable region for honey production. Spreading the flowering time throughout the year and having a rich flora positively affects honey production. Considering its contributions to human health, agricultural production and economy, beekeeping is very important for the Mediterranean region.

Beekeeping is an important farming activity and bee products are valuable for balanced and healthy human nutrition. In addition, bees are very important in maintaining ecological balance and agricultural production by pollinating plants. Beekeeping provides employment, income and healthy nutrition to the rural population. Considering the impact of the nutritional needs of the increasing population, various policies are implemented to support and encourage beekeeping in the world. The increase in the use of honey as an alternative to artificial sweeteners in recent years shows that the market for bee products will grow. In addition to honey production, the production and trade of royal jelly, pollen, propolis, bee venom and beeswax is a necessity in order to reduce the risks that may arise from a possible decrease in honey yield and to prevent producers from suffering losses.

Increased production can be achieved by using good agricultural techniques and controlling the widespread use of pesticides associated with industrial agriculture. Reducing the unit cost in production and establishing a standardized production type increases both efficiency and quality.

The growth rate of the beekeeping sector is slowing down, especially under the pressure of environmental factors. Increasing the growth rate will be achieved by revealing the effectiveness of the implemented policies and directing the support areas according to this effectiveness.

The number of practices such as courses and low-interest loans that will especially encourage young entrepreneurs and women to take part in activities should be increased and the sector should be further supported with new R and D projects.

Conscious consumers have a great impact on honey quality, affordable and value prices, trouble-free markets and healthy living. For this purpose, consumers need to be further informed. The quality of honey produced should be controlled and food controls should be increased. Thus, consumers should be protected against adulterated honey.

Therefore, novel policy strategies should be based on:

- Geographical Indications (GIs): GIs enhance local economic development by promoting regional products and tourism.
- Traceability and Labeling: Enforcing clear labeling indicating origin, processing methods, additives, and other information.
- Sustainable Production
- Quality Standards and Testing
- Research and Development Support
- Funding research into improving honeybee health, combating colony collapse disorder, and finding alternatives to harmful pesticides.
- Supporting innovations in honey production, quality, and packaging.
- Economic and Trade Policies
- Consumer Education

Promoting MEDIFIT solutions for digital traceability in the food industry involves the implementation of policy instruments that encourage the adoption of digital technologies to track and trace food products throughout the supply chain. Several policy instruments can be employed to support food digital traceability:

- Mandatory Digital Traceability Regulations:

Governments can enact laws that make digital traceability mandatory for certain types of food products or within specific sectors of the food industry. This could involve requirements for the use of specific technologies, such as barcodes, RFID, or blockchain, and the maintenance of electronic records.

- Technology Standards and Certification:

Establishing digital traceability standards that define the requirements for technology use and data management. Certification programs can be developed to verify that businesses comply with these standards, offering assurance to consumers and facilitating interoperability.

- Financial Incentives for Technology Adoption:

Providing financial incentives, tax credits, or grants to food businesses that invest in and adopt digital traceability technologies. This can help offset the initial costs associated with implementing these systems.

- Research and Development Support:

Allocating funds for research and development projects focused on improving digital traceability technologies. This may include supporting initiatives that explore the integration of emerging technologies like artificial intelligence or the Internet of Things (IoT) in traceability systems.

- Capacity Building and Training:

Offering training programs and educational resources to help businesses understand and implement digital traceability systems effectively. This can include technical training, workshops, and seminars.

- Open Data Initiatives:

Encouraging the development and adoption of open data standards that facilitate data exchange and interoperability among different actors in the supply chain. Open data initiatives can promote transparency and collaboration.

- Cybersecurity and Data Protection Regulations:

Implementing regulations to ensure the security and protection of digital traceability data. These regulations can establish standards for data encryption, access controls, and measures to prevent unauthorized access and data breaches.

- Collaborative Platforms and Industry Consortia:

Supporting the creation of collaborative platforms or industry consortia that bring together stakeholders, including government agencies, businesses, and technology providers, to develop and promote common digital traceability solutions.

- Monitoring and Auditing Mechanisms:

Establishing mechanisms for regular monitoring, auditing, and verification of digital traceability systems. This can involve inspections by regulatory bodies or third-party auditors to ensure compliance with established standards.

- International Cooperation and Standardization:

Collaborating with international organizations and other countries to harmonize digital traceability standards. This can facilitate global trade and information exchange while ensuring consistency in traceability practices.

- Incentives for Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs):

Providing targeted support and incentives for small and medium-sized enterprises to adopt digital traceability solutions. This can include grants, training programs, and simplified compliance procedures.

Therefore, effective policy development for digital traceability involves considering a combination of these instruments to create a comprehensive framework that fosters the widespread adoption of digital technologies across the food supply chain.

To foster transitions towards a new paradigm of digital food companies using EPCIS 2.0, several steps must be taken in a longer-term perspective:

Awareness and Education

- Raise awareness about the benefits and capabilities of EPCIS 2.0.
- Offer training and workshops to industry stakeholders on how to implement and leverage EPCIS 2.0 for supply chain visibility and efficiency.

Infrastructure Development

- Ensure the existence of robust IT infrastructure that supports the implementation and scaling of EPCIS 2.0.
- Promote the development of software platforms and applications tailored to EPCIS 2.0.

Collaboration and Standardization

- Foster collaboration between stakeholders – from farmers and manufacturers to retailers and consumers.
- Encourage industry-wide adoption of EPCIS 2.0 to ensure data consistency and interoperability.

Data Privacy and Security

- Implement robust data security measures to ensure the protection of data shared across the supply chain.
- Educate stakeholders about data privacy regulations and best practices.

Integration with Emerging Technologies

- Promote the integration of EPCIS 2.0 with other emerging technologies such as IoT, AI, and machine learning.

- Develop systems where EPCIS events can trigger machine learning models leading to advanced analytics and predictions.

Regulatory Support

- Engage with regulatory bodies to ensure that EPCIS 2.0's capabilities align with current and future regulations, especially in the food sector.
- Advocate for policies that support the digital transformation of the food industry using standards like EPCIS 2.0.

Feedback Mechanisms

- Establish systems to gather feedback from stakeholders on challenges and improvements related to EPCIS 2.0 implementation.
- Continuously refine and update the standard based on industry needs. (through GS1 EPCIS related work-requests)

Consumer Engagement

- Educate consumers about the benefits of EPCIS 2.0-driven transparency, such as improved product authenticity and traceability.
- Develop consumer-facing applications that leverage EPCIS 2.0 data, offering insights into product journey, authenticity, and other relevant information.

Economic Incentives

- Offer financial incentives or subsidies to companies, especially in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), to adopt and implement EPCIS 2.0.
- Recognize and reward early adopters and innovators in the domain.

Research and Development

- Foster R&D initiatives that aim to expand the capabilities of EPCIS 2.0 in the food sector.
- Continue Collaboration with academic institutions and research organizations to explore new applications and improvements.

Cultural Shift

- Encourage a culture of transparency, collaboration, and innovation within the food industry.
- Promote the values of ethical sourcing, sustainability, and consumer trust, all of which can be enhanced by EPCIS 2.0.

New value chains and business opportunities

In the rapidly evolving landscape of food traceability, specialized tools are being implemented in the honey and cheese industries.

For honey, emerging opportunities lie in geographical origin verification, hive monitoring through IoT integration, and blockchain-based authentication. Quality control and consumer engagement platforms further enhance transparency and trust. The combination of a dynamic shelf-life and quality of fresh produce together with dynamic pricing - integrated in an expert solution - will impact in reducing food waste and improving financial performance, and thus entailing major benefits for veg SMEs. Biofresh Cloud provides an integrated, innovative, and eco-friendly approach to assess optimal shelf-life and minimize food losses of strawberries and tomatoes produced in the Mediterranean region, by combining food bio[1]preservation technologies, food modeling, and Food Cloud tools. The technological solutions encapsulates a sustainable and circular view, making use and valorising Mediterranean agri-food resources to develop natural preservatives, extending food shelf-life and providing safer and fresher products to consumers.

"Contracted Beekeeping Model" is a business model in which production contracts are made directly with beekeepers, and correct beekeeping practices are targeted in the field. Additionally, the naturalness and food safety compliance of bee products are verified through analysis, and their biological activities are maintained before they reach consumers. In the "Contracted Beekeeping" model, we first meet beekeepers throughout Anatolia who can produce bee products under a production contract with the assistance of our agricultural engineers. We check the beekeeper's apiary first to ensure that it is located in places with clean water sources, no waste, and factories in the vicinity, away from the road and pesticide-free areas. Thus, we protect the naturalness of our products at every step of production. We attach great importance to our contracted beekeepers not leaving residue-producing pesticides when producing bee products. After acquiring with our beekeepers, we provide them with the necessary equipment to collect propolis and other bee products. Our beekeepers cleanly package the collected bee products and send them to our facilities. Our expert engineers test the products, and their quality is ensured. After these controls, value-added bee products traceable from the hive to the table are produced. Thanks to our Contracted Beekeeping Model, we offer our products to consumers 100% natural and pure by controlling them at every stage. In addition to providing equipment support to our beekeepers, we guarantee their

payments. With this model, we eliminate intermediaries and realize "fair trade" by ensuring beekeepers earn income directly.

Furthermore, as part of the social responsibility project carried out, 1% of the income from each product sold is collected in a fund to provide beekeepers with more modern equipment to contribute to the sustainability of beekeeping. This money accumulated in the fund is returned to beekeepers to renew their equipment, such as honey extraction machines, modern beehives, honey settling tanks, pollen traps, etc. Thus, the development and sustainability of beekeeping in our country is supported.

In the cheese sector, software solutions are poised to optimize milk source verification, aging and maturation monitoring, and supply chain logistics. MicroHibro is an online free access tool, developed by MEDIFIT Partner, University of Cordoba (González et al., 2019), integrating the application of predictive microbiology models and quantitative microbiological risk assessment in foods. Advanced analytics enable precise grading and classification, while compliance management ensures adherence to industry standards. Waste reduction and sustainability efforts are also gaining traction. Retail and distribution platforms are streamlining transactions and bolstering traceability across the cheese supply chain. These innovations signify a promising frontier, where technology meets the demand for authenticity, quality, and transparency in food production.

New business opportunities can facilitate exploitation of EPCIS protocols by third parties (e.g., through making results available under open licenses). The main objective is to exploit the results generated by the project by ensuring a smooth transfer to all potential beneficiaries (from civil society to the scientific community) and for tapping into the potential of "valorization" of project results (either commercially or scientifically) as far as it is possible. Market strategies may be oriented to activities of mainstreaming (successful transfer of project results to appropriate stakeholders and decision-makers) and multiplication (convincing other end-users to adopt or apply the outputs of the project). Target groups for exploitation activities are :

- i) Public authorities, whose will use the EPCIS protocol to monitor, verify and decide the acceptability of food batches according to international standards;
- ii) SME Suppliers, who are small producers having the need of improving traceability and authenticity of their products, through a cost-effective solution technology;
- iii) Large companies having different independent headquarters (cooperatives) needing an interconnexion between companies and a data sharing system; and
- iv) Logistic/supply chains, comprising both the physical flow of goods and the associated flow of information.

In this context, new value chains and business opportunities are :

Enhanced Traceability & Authenticity

- Premium Authentic Products: With improved traceability, producers can market their cheese and honey as authentic and genuine, fetching premium prices.

Data-Driven Insights

- By capturing and analyzing data throughout the production process, producers can identify inefficiencies and optimize production techniques.

Demand Forecasting

- Integration of EPCIS data with machine learning models can provide accurate demand forecasting, reducing wastage and ensuring timely production.

Consumer Engagement

- Interactive Labels
- QR codes or NFC tags can be used on cheese and honey packaging.
- When scanned, these can lead consumers to a platform showing the product's journey, validated by EPCIS 2.0 data.

Loyalty Programs

- Engage consumers by offering rewards for purchasing authenticated products, driving repeat sales.

Supply Chain Optimization

- Real-time visibility into product movement can help in better inventory management, reducing holding costs and wastage.
- With better visibility into the supply chain, businesses can implement dynamic pricing strategies based on demand and supply.

Collaborative Opportunities

- Cheese and honey producers can collaborate with tech providers to create integrated solutions, combining IoT sensors and EPCIS 2.0 standards.
- Third-party agencies can offer certification services for cheese and honey producers, verifying and authenticating their traceability practices based on EPCIS 2.0 data.

Sustainable Practices

- Efficient tracking can lead to reduced wastage in the supply chain.
- Eco Branding: With transparent practices, producers can position their products as sustainably produced, appealing to eco-conscious consumers.

Marketplace & Platforms

- Specialized Online Marketplaces: Platforms dedicated to authenticated cheese and honey products, ensuring consumers get genuine products.
- B2B Platforms: Platforms where producers can showcase their traceability practices to attract bulk buyers or retailers.

Conclusion

Actually the beekeeping sector faces multiple challenges, the most important of which is climate change. In this work we have taken stock of the situation and issued a series of recommendations in response to the challenges identified. It is clear that the alteration of the environment and the health of bees has significant consequences not only on productivity, honey production and biodiversity, therefore on the profitability of beekeeping and agricultural operations, on rural development, but also on the health of the population. The cause is a combination of abiotic and biotic factors, the most important being climate change. Biodiversity and climate are closely inter-correlated. It is therefore necessary to anticipate the future impact of climate change and agricultural land management on pollinators and the beekeeping business. To this end, it is important to take measures to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and protect the natural habitats of bees. Farmers must work closely with beekeepers, use sustainable agricultural practices such as efficient water management, use of disease-resistant seeds, crop rotation, and avoid the use of pesticides. We must also take health issues into account when practicing beekeeping and promote sustainable practices to minimize their impact on food security, public health and ecosystems. Indeed, the poor beekeeping practices observed highlight problems of supervision, technical assistance and agricultural advice as well as a lack of training/extension.

Technological innovations can contribute to helping beekeepers overcome climatic, health and socio-economic challenges, and improve the productivity and profitability of their operations. In reality, these challenges for the beekeeping industry require a comprehensive approach that involves the collaboration of all stakeholders, including beekeepers, farmers, scientists, governments, professional organizations and international NGOs. Broader societal efforts must also be made to combat climate change, such as decarbonization of the energy and transport sectors and carbon capture strategies of various types, and the promotion of sustainable consumption patterns. Concerning the problem of fraud, the authorities must constantly seek ways to reassure consumers about the origin, safety and quality of products, and to encourage actors in the value chain to respect regulations and consumers to self-authenticate food products.

The development of digital solutions to guarantee the traceability and authenticity of food, from farm to fork, as in the European PRIMA-MEDIFIT project (2020-2023), based on the use of the latest analytical and software technologies (EPCIS, Microhibro), will allow beekeepers better accessibility to a traceability system, and consumers to self-authenticate themselves the products in food stores. Finally, to effectively tackle the challenges faced by the Mediterranean region, it will be interesting to promote the adoption of the MEDIFIT integrated approach. This will require the EU to engage in policy dialogues centered on research and innovation. In fact, the establishment of a significant stride towards the formation of a union among Southern neighborhood countries is underway and the development of a shared research and innovation agenda within the Mediterranean region is a key focus of the Knowledge and Innovation Area (CKIS).

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